

Aquinas on the Fullness of the Grace of Mary

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Introduction

Within Christianity, Mary, Jesus' mother, has long been a source of adoration and interest. Her „fullness of grace” has drawn particular attention as a trait of her character. This idea contends that Mary was specially chosen and prepared by God to bring the Son of God into the world. It is based on the New Testament account of the Annunciation. Throughout Christian history, the concept of Mary's fullness of grace has been a topic of theological discussion and debate, with ramifications for discussions about Mariology, soteriology, and other topics. The concept of Mary's fullness of grace has inspired and aroused debate

among theologians and believers alike because it argues that she was specially selected and prepared by God to bring the Son of God into the world.

Though the idea of Mary's fullness of grace has a long tradition, it is nevertheless the focus of theological discussion today. Some theologians have stressed Mary's unique place in salvation history, contending that it was only by the fullness of her grace that she was able to carry the Son of God and completely take part in his redemptive mission. Others have been more circumspect, pointing out that it can be challenging to articulate the concept of fullness of

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grace and that it could be problematic if it indicates that Mary was sinless or divine. The idea of Mary's fullness of grace is still a hot topic in modern Christian theology despite these disa-

greements. We intend to investigate the concept's biblical roots, early Christian growth, and continued theological significance from the lenses of Aquinas in this article.

Aquinas' Concept of Divine Grace

Divine grace is the gratuitous gift of God whereby He moves the subject of the gift to know or will or act. It is also a habitual gift infused into the soul, by which man is aided by God's gratuitous will. As a result, it becomes more appropriate for God to supply more for those He loves in order for them to acquire supernatural goods than for the creatures He loves in order for them to acquire natural goods. Furthermore, through this gift, He lavishes upon individuals' specific forms and capacities, which are the principles of operations, in order that they may be disposed to the divine will of their own accord. As a result, the movements by which He moves natural creatures become natural and simple to creatures, as stated in Wisdom 8:1: „She (...) arranges everything in a lovely manner". He imparts certain forms or mystical characteristics into those He moves toward attainment of supernatural good, so that they may be turned by Him sweetly and speedily to earn eternal good¹.

To further clarify the concept of grace, let us differentiate it from virtue. According to Aristotle, virtue is the disposition of what is perfect, and by we

conceive perfection as one's disposition in accordance with his essence². Since everything is arranged in accordance with what is appropriate for its nature, it follows that a thing's value has some connection to an underlying nature. However, it is clear that human virtues result in a man being appropriately disposed in relation to his form. Grace on the other hand is according to 2 Peter 1:4: „He has given us most great and most precious promises; that by these you may be made partakers of the Divine Nature", infused virtues position man in a higher manner and towards a higher end and, as a result, in relation to some higher nature, i.e., in relation to a participation of the Divine Nature. We are considered sons of God who have been reborn in the light of getting this nature³. Also, while virtues reside in the powers of the soul, grace resides in the essence of the soul. The fact that grace comes before virtue means that it has a subject that comes before the powers of the soul, making it part of the soul's essential nature. Because just as man shares in the divine knowledge through the virtue of faith and shares in the divine love through the virtue of charity

¹ *S. th.*, I-II, q. 110, a. 2, co.

² Aristotle, *Physics* VII, 17.

³ *S. th.*, I-II, q. 110, a. 3, co.

with his will and willpower, so too does he share in the Divine Nature with his soul in a like manner through a specific regeneration or re-creation⁴.

From this definition above we can deduce that Mary received the divine gratuitous gift to know, will and act supernaturally, with specific forms and capacities, which are the principles of operations, in order that she may be disposed to the divine will of her own ac-

cord. The grace she received empowered her to be full of virtues and to act naturally to the perfection of her substance and the grace also made her act supernaturally in relation to God's will. The fullness of her virtues is in her power but the fullness of the grace gifted to her is in her substance. The angel hailed Mary as full of grace, let us explore the meaning of that.

The Fullness of Divine Grace in Mary

Now that we have an idea of what Mary was gifted under the name „grace”, it is fitting we proceed further to examine what the angel meant by „full of grace” (Luke 1:28), and the extent of the fullness of her grace. For Aquinas, to possess something fully is to acquire it

wholly and perfectly⁵. Now let us explore the concept of fullness under the lenses of perfection as defined by Aquinas. Then the types of perfection, the nature of the fullness of Mary's grace, the degrees of perfection and the most fitting place for Mary among creatures.

The Concept of Perfection

So, what is perfection for Aquinas? According to Thomas, it is „that which is excellent in itself, lacking nothing that pertains to it”⁶. He contends that everything aspires to perfection and that this effort shows that they share in God's perfection. In other words, everything is „perfect” to the degree that it exhibits the excellence of God. According to Aquinas, God, is „the first cause, the ultimate end, and the absolute model of all perfection”, He is the source of all perfection⁷. The Angelic Doctor con-

tends that since God is the foundation of all perfection, our ultimate aim as beings is to pursue union with God in order to experience perfect happiness.

Aquinas defined perfection as the condition in which an entity has achieved all of the features and characteristics required for its proper operation as well as a complete realization of its nature. According to its essence, a perfect entity has no deficiencies⁸. Additionally, perfection is attained when a being has realized all of its potential and

⁴ *S. th.*, I-II, q. 110, a. 3, co.

⁵ *S. th.*, III, q. 7, a. 9, co.

⁶ *S. th.*, I, q. 4, a. 2, co.

⁷ *Ibidem*.

⁸ *De Veritate*, q. 21, a. 1.

evolved into everything it was intended to be. When all of an entity's potentialities are completely realized, perfection is the fullness of being⁹. In addition, Aquinas argued that goodness originates from perfection, which is both the ultimate objective of all things and the source of all goodness. Since perfection is the condition in which every being have fully realized their inherent abilities and has become everything that they were meant to be, it is the ultimate goal toward which everything tends¹⁰. Realizing potential and aligning one's will with the heavenly Will are two other ways that perfection can be attained. Aligning one's will completely with the divine Will, in which all thoughts and deeds are in conformity with God's design, is what it means to be perfect¹¹.

Furthermore, an entity reaches perfection when it is without any flaws and has attained the fullness of its essence. When a subject has accomplished everything required for it to operate

properly and has realized its full potential, it is said to be perfect¹². Aquinas also defined perfection as the condition in which an entity has realized its complete potential and is entirely true to its nature. When something reaches its full potential and becomes everything it was intended to be, it is perfect¹³. Aquinas believed that an entity can only reach completeness when it is completely at peace with both itself and its surroundings. When an entity is completely incorporated into its natural surroundings and is operating in perfect harmony with its circumstances, it is perfect¹⁴. Thomas holds that an entity reaches perfection when it possesses all of the traits and characteristics required for it to operate properly. When an object has everything, it requires to accomplish its goals and realize its full potential, it is perfect¹⁵. According to Aquinas, an entity has attained perfection when it has fulfilled its ultimate goal and completely assimilated into divine providence¹⁶.

On the Principal Way of Fullness

Wholeness and perfection can now be interpreted in terms of their „intensive” quantity; for example, we might say that a man has height fully because he possesses as much of it as is naturally possible in him¹⁷. Christ possesses grace

to the fullest extent in the most perfect way it can be had. The indication of this is the proximity of Christ's soul to the origin of grace (His Divine Nature). A recipient gets more the closer it is to the inflowing cause. As a result, God's gra-

⁹ *Scg*, I, c. 22.

¹⁰ *S. th.*, II-II, q. 184, a. 3, co.

¹¹ *S. th.*, I, q. 2, a. 3, co.

¹² *De potentia*, q. 3, a. 8.

¹³ *S. th.*, I, q. 4, a. 1.

¹⁴ *De veritate*, q. 21, a. 1.

¹⁵ *S. th.*, I, q. 39, a. 8, co.

¹⁶ *S. th.*, I, q. 42, a. 1, co.

¹⁷ *S. th.*, III, q. 7, a. 9, co.

ce is most abundantly shown to Christ's soul, which is most closely connected to God than any other rational creation (angelic or human)¹⁸. The implication in the context of our research is that the strongest and closest tie between creation in its entirety and the Divine Nature is the hypostatic union. By the reality that Mary is also full of grace, it implies that the maternal relationship between Christ and Mary is the second strongest and closest relationship not only to humanity but to all creatures (angelic creatures included).

Let us examine briefly the hypostatic union which is the strongest and nearest relation to the Divine Nature. At first inspection, it might seem preferable to conceive of Christ as completely simple or incomposite. As Thomas explains in the *Summa theologiae* I, q. 3, every divine individual is simple, and Christ is divine. As a result, the simplicity of Christ seems to be implied by the integrity of his divinity. The integrity of his humanity would appear to be compromised if we insisted on this issue. For starters, if Christ is only divine, he is unable to possess human essence; consequently, he is unable to be human. Furthermore, since humans are inherently made up of a variety of parts, Christ cannot be simple or without any parts in any manner. To give clarity to this, Aquinas said: „The person or hypostasis of Christ can be considered in two ways. The first way is according to the way it exists in itself. And in this way, it is complete as is the nature of the

Word. The second way is according to the way it exists as a person or hypostasis that subsists in some nature. In this way, the person of Christ subsists in two natures. Whence, although there is only one subsisting thing in this case, there is nonetheless a plurality of manners of subsistence. And thus, he can be called a composite person, in so far as he is one thing subsisting in two ways”¹⁹.

A supposit can be viewed in two different ways. At first, we merely think of it as something that is existing, regardless of the essence or natures in which it is existing. For instance, we can ignore the reality that Christ exists as both God and a human being and simply think of Him as a person who exists²⁰. In the second method, we regard a supposit to be real in some sense. Christ is one such illustration of a being that is both divine and human. When we consider Christ in the second sense, that is, in light of how He subsists Himself, we must categorize him as composite, the union of His divine and human natures in His person.

The concept of Christ's compositeness cannot be completely appreciated without also understanding Christ's non-compositeness. Near the conclusion of the passage, Thomas clarifies his statement that Christ is simple insofar as He exists in Himself by using the phrase “one subsisting thing”. This should be understood as follows. Christ exists, and He does so because He is the Word. He derives His absolute existence – His existence as understood

¹⁸ *Ibidem*.

¹⁹ *S. th.*, III, q. 2, a. 4, co.

²⁰ D. Legge, *Thomas Aquinas on the Incarnation: An Introduction*, Ave Maria Press, 2017, p. 23.

apart from any character – not from His human nature (otherwise he wouldn't have existed prior to becoming human) but rather from His status as the divine Word. But the Holy Word itself is very simple. Christ is therefore simple in Himself. This simplicity fits with the structure we've already talked about. Christ is a supposit because of just one of His natures, but that doesn't mean He doesn't have another²¹.

Thomas, therefore, believes that Christ is a composite, and because of this, he is able to respond to a particular argument that questions the consistency of Christ's godhead. Christ is composite in that he possesses two natures, allowing him to possess a human nature and all of its components. This preserves the purity of Christ's humanity. Additionally, the integrity of Christ's divinity is preserved because this composition is one of the natures present in the entire individual rather than a composition of the Divine Nature²². Aquinas adds to his fundamental theory to make it more appropriate by asserting that the hypostatic union produces a composite person. Aquinas emphasizes that the union of natures in Christ is not a blending or mixture of the two, but a subsistence of one nature in another²³. The hypostatic union involves the communication of

attributes or properties between the two natures of Christ²⁴. Aquinas stresses that the hypostatic union is a mystery that human reason cannot fully grasp²⁵.

Having argued that is the fullness of grace, let us see why Mary is said to be favoured with full grace. In every genus, the closer a creature is to the principle, the greater the role it has in the effects of that principle. For this reason, Dionysius claims in that because angels are closer to God than mortals, they have a bigger share than men in the effects of Divine goodness²⁶. According to John 1:17, „Grace and truth came by Jesus Christ”, which means that Christ is the principle of grace in both His Godhead and humanity. However, because He inherited His human nature from the Blessed Virgin Mary, Christ is closest to her in terms of His humanity, Christ's humanity is the instrument for the dispensing of grace and since Mary is the closest to the human nature of Christ, she receives the most. She was therefore entitled to receive more grace than other people²⁷. This argument explicitly reveals how Mary possesses full grace than other mortals but it is not so obvious yet how her grace exceeds those of the angels.

To demonstrate even further that Mary's grace outranks every other cre-

²¹ N. Kretzmann, E. Stump (ed.), *The Cambridge Companion to Thomas Aquinas*, Cambridge University Press, 1993, p. 256.

²² G.R. Evans, *Aquinas and the Nicene Creed: An Introduction to the Philosophy of Religion*, Continuum 2003, pp.135-138; see also M.A. Gillespie, *The Theological Origins of Modernity*, University of Chicago Press 2008.

²³ D. Legge, *Thomas Aquinas on the Incarnation: An Introduction*, p. 28.

²⁴ *Ibidem*, p. 37.

²⁵ *Ibidem*, p. 38.

²⁶ *Coel. Hier.* IV.

²⁷ *S. th.*, III, q. 27, a. 5, co.

ated person, this argument of Aquinas seems adequate. God provides to each person in accordance with the reason He elected them. According to John 1:16: „Of His fulness, we have all received”, Christ in His humanity is to have such a fulness of grace that poured from Him into everyone because He was predestined and elected to be „predestined the Son of God in power (...) of sanctification” (Romans 1:4). This was due to His human nature being predestined and chosen. The Blessed Virgin Mary, on the other hand, was given such an abundance of grace that she is the closest of all to the Giver of grace. As a result, she carried within her the One who is the fullness of all grace, and by bringing Him into the world, she in a sense distributed grace to everyone²⁸. So, Mary is the created person with the fullest grace even above the angels firstly she was destined to do so, secondly, she carried the Principle of grace Himself.

When it comes to natural things, the matter is initially perfectly disposed, for example when it is disposed for a particular form. The second is the perfection of the form, which is even better since the heat that emanates from fire is more perfect than the heat that is directed toward the fire. Thirdly, there is the perfection of the result, as when a fire has attained its own location and has achieved all of its qualities to the highest degree. Applying this principle, Aquinas said: „In like manner, there was a threefold perfection of grace in the Blessed Virgin. The first was a kind

of disposition, by which she was made worthy to be the mother of Christ: and this was the perfection of her sanctification. The second perfection of grace in the Blessed Virgin was through the presence of the Son of God Incarnate in her womb. The third perfection of the end is that which she has in glory. Likewise, as regards the «virtue» of grace, He had grace fully, since He had it for all the operations and effects of grace; and this, because grace was bestowed on Him, as upon a universal principle in the genus of such as have grace. Now the virtue of the first principle of a genus universally extends itself to all the effects of that genus; thus, the force of the sun, which is the universal cause of generation, as Dionysius says (*Div. Nom.* I), extends to all things that come under generation. Hence the second fulness of grace is seen in Christ inasmuch as His grace extends to all the effects of grace, which are the virtues, gifts, and the like²⁹.

Lastly, on this point concerning the fullness of the graces received by Mary, it would seem she did not receive all graces because God will not give her graces she will not put into use as it will be useless to her purpose. Responding to this, Aquinas said Mary received all the graces even if she will not use them but it befitted her status, citing an instance he quoted Luke 2:19 „But Mary kept all these words, pondering them in her heart”. But she had not the use of wisdom as to teaching: since this befitted not the female sex, according to 1

²⁸ *S. th.*, III, q. 27, a. 5, ad. 1.

²⁹ *S. th.*, III, q. 27, a. 5, ad. 2.

Timothy 2:12: „But I suffer not a woman to teach”. The use of miracles did not become her while she lived: because at that time the Teaching of Christ was to

be confirmed by miracles, and therefore it was befitting that Christ alone, and His disciples who were the bearers of His doctrine, should work miracles³⁰.

On the Possession of the Fullness of Grace

One can interpret the fullness of grace in two distinct manners: firstly, on the part of the grace itself and secondly, on the side of the one who is graced. The first distinctive way is when the peak of grace is reached in terms of essence and power, it is deemed to be the fulness of grace since it is possessed in its highest conceivable perfection and in its fullest expansion to all of its manifestations. In this light, it is exclusive to Christ to be entitled to this fullness of grace³¹. For He is the zenith of grace; the length, width, height and depth of grace. No grace is received if it is not from Him, He is the principal source of grace.

In the second distinctive manner, Thomas cited Ephesians 4:1 „But to each of us is given grace according to the measure of the giving of Christ” to express his point. One is deemed to have the fulness of grace when the person fully demonstrates it according to his divinely designated circumstance, whether as regards intensity because grace is intense in the person to the extent assigned by God, or „as regards power” because the recipient has the assistance of grace for all that is associated with his office or state³². And this fullness of grace is not proper to Christ but is communicated to others by Christ.

The most appropriate person or the highest person this second way is proper to is Mary. This is because she has the highest designated office or status as the mother of God. So, in this sense, Mary possesses the fullness of grace that God designated to other creatures angelic or human save His human nature.

Mary is referred to as being full of grace, but not in terms of grace itself – since she did not possess grace in its highest possible excellence – nor in terms of all the effects of grace. Rather, she is referred to as being full of grace in terms of herself, meaning that she had enough grace to fulfil the role that God had assigned her, namely that of being the mother of His Only-begotten. Stephen is sometimes referred to as being „full of grace” because he possessed enough grace to be a suitable minister and witness for God, offices to which he had been appointed³³. And the same is true for other people, for instance, the angels and in this instance the Seraphim may be said to possess the fullness of grace. One is greater than another in this fullness, depending on whether they were divinely predestined for a higher or lower position and Mary occupies the top of the ladder.

³⁰ *S. th.*, III, q. 27, a. 5, ad. 3.

³¹ *S. th.*, III, q. 7, a. 10, co.

³² *Ibidem*.

³³ *S. th.*, III, q. 7, a. 10, ad. 1.

The Finiteness of the Grace in Mary

Despite that there is the fullness of grace in Mary according to her office or status, there is some finiteness of grace in Mary, on this point Thomas said „grace is something created in the soul. But every created thing is finite, according to Wisdom 11:21: «Thou hast ordered all things in measure, number, and weight». Therefore, the grace of Christ’s humanity is not infinite”³⁴. Mary is a created being, therefore, in this way, Mary’s grace is finite. Arguing further on this point, Aquinas posited that habitual grace can be interpreted in one of two ways: first, as a being, in which case it must be a finite being because Mary’s soul is a creature with a finite capacity and, as such, the volume of grace is unable to be infinite because it cannot be greater than its subject which is finite³⁵. Second, it may be seen as a finite nature of grace received, but in this finiteness, the grace is poured out indefinitely because it contains everything that is possible with regard to that particular nature of grace, and what is possible with regard to that nature of grace is not given to her in a set amount. In other words, Mary’s grace is limited in the sense that it is appropriate for her nature as human but limitless in the sense that she is graced with all that is proper to her motherhood³⁶.

Explaining further, the finiteness of grace in Mary, we will use what Aquinas’ thought about the limitedness of grace in the human nature of Christ to

further argue the finiteness of the grace of Mary. If Mary is full of grace, then there cannot be an increase of grace in her because she is full of grace according to the manner already treated above. Now, a form might become incapable of growth in two different ways: first, from the subject; and second, from the form itself. On the aspect of the subject, in fact, when the subject reaches the maximum extent at which it participates in this form, in accordance with its own manner, for example, if a jar of water is the subject and water is the form when the jar is filled to the brim, the form which is the water in this instance that not be increased, so in this instance it is limited.

In a second way, when a subject reaches the highest degree of perfection that this form is capable of having by nature, the prospect of growth is excluded on the side of the form. For instance, we may state that the heat of a fire cannot be raised because there is no higher degree of heat than what a fire can produce. Wisdom 11:21 states that Divine wisdom, like that of other kinds, decides the appropriate measure of grace: „Thou hast numbered, weighed, and measured all things”. And each shape has a measure that is determined in relation to its goal. because there is no place lower than the earth, and there is no gravity stronger than that of the ground itself.

³⁴ *S. th.*, III, q. 7, a. 11, sc.

³⁵ *S. th.*, III, q. 7, a. 10, co.

³⁶ *Ibidem*.

Having these two ways in mind, let us apply them to the instance of Mary. The connection of the intellectual creature with God is the culmination of grace. However, there is no greater unity between God and the rational creature than that which exists in the individual. And hence the grace of Mary reached the highest measure of grace at conception as regards her body, the fullness of grace with the conception of Christ as regards her soul because she was united with God in her womb. Hence it is clear that the grace of Mary cannot be increased on the part of grace. But neither can it be increased on the part of the subject, since only Mary had a di-

rect bodily connection with the human nature of Christ who has the fullness of union with the divinity of Christ in His person, Mary is the first beneficiary of the hypostatic union. Hence there could have been no increase of grace in her matter and soul while still on earth, seeing that she had reached her last end. But as regards men who are wholly wayfarers, their grace can be increased not merely on the part of the form, since they have not attained the highest degree of grace, but also on the part of the subject, since they have not yet attained their end, meaning Mary attained her fullest end in her glorification in heaven.

Conclusion

We can infer that Mary was given the gratuitous ability by God to know, will, and act supernaturally, with particular forms and capacities, which are the principles of operations, in order to be naturally inclined to the will of God. The grace she received enabled her to act naturally in accordance with the perfection of her substance, to be full of virtues, and to act supernaturally in accordance with God's will. Her power reflects the depth of her virtues, but her substance reflects the fullness of the grace that was bestowed upon her.

Mary is said to possess grace fully because she has wholly and entirely all the graces that are given by God to every creature in the fullest receivable

measure in comparison to other intellectual creatures save the humanity of Christ and this is befitting of her office as the Mother of God. She had all graces whether actively used or not. Mary acquired this privilege of the fullness of grace due to the proximity of her relation to Christ's humanity. The fullness of her grace happened in three ways, as regards her body that relates to her Immaculate Conception, as regards her soul when she conceived Christ and the finality of her fullness of grace in her person as regards her glorification in heaven. The grace in her is finite in a universal sense because she has a finite nature, but as pertains to the graces she receives, it is in the fullness of measures.

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Pełnia łaski w Maryi według Tomasza z Akwinu

Słowa kluczowe: Maryja, Chrystus, Pełna łaski, Łaska, Tomasz z Akwinu

Szerszy teologiczny kontekst, w jakim Tomasz z Akwinu podkreślał znaczenie boskiej łaski w zbawieniu ludzkim, stanowi podstawę uznania wyjątkowego miejsca Maryi w historii zbawienia i określenie jej jako pełnej łaski. W opinii Akwinaty, wybór Maryi przez Boga na Matkę Bożą nie był niezależny od obfitości łaski jaką posiadała, co w dalszej konsekwencji umożliwiło jej pełne uczestnictwo w planie zbawienia Boga. Koncepcja pełni łaski w Maryi zakorzeniona w pozdrowieniu anioła i w sformułowaniach dogmatu Niepokalanego Poczęcia Maryi prowadzi do

dalszych pytań: „Jeśli jest pełna łaski od samego początku, czy nie otrzymała łaski, gdy nosiła Chrystusa?”, a także „Czy fakt bycia pełną łaski oznacza, że w chwale w niebie nic nie zostało jej dodane?”. Niniejszy artykuł jest propozycją przyjrzenia się myśli Akwinaty na temat pełni łaski w Maryi. W artykule podkreśla się trwałе teologiczne znaczenie tego konceptu dla współczesnej teologii chrześcijańskiej. W niniejszej propozycji wyjaśnia się złożone powiązania między łaską, wolną wolą a odkupieniem, prezentując nowe spojrzenie na rolę Maryi w tradycji chrześcijańskiej.